

CFD Modelling of Liquid Hydrogen Containment

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ABSTRACT

Accurate prediction of pressurisation and sloshing in cryogenic containment tanks is critical for reliable tank pressure control. This work validates the in-house ELEMENTAL® AlphaFlow commercial software against two benchmark liquid hydrogen (LH₂) experiments: the recent SHIIVER (Johnson et al. 2024) passive pressurisation test and the pressure collapse due violent slosh of Moran et al. (1994). Simulations are performed using real and ideal gas models coupled with an incompressible Boussinesq liquid approximation. Suitability of the gas models for the experimental conditions is assessed. For SHIIVER, the 70% fill-level passive pressurisation case is for the first time simulated. Notably, a thin wall conjugate-heat-transfer model is used to capture the redistribution of heat flux between the liquid and vapour regions with its validity verified via wall Biot number analysis. Interfacial heat and mass transfer are resolved using a sharp-gradient based method which is also applied to the mass transfer calculation. Predicted pressurisation rates agree with experimental data to within 2% on a coarse grid and 1% on a fine grid demonstrating grid convergence and accurate thermal-fluid wall coupling. For the violent slosh case, the 36% fill level case is modelled. No phase change nor conjugate-heat-transfer effects are included. Here, a calibrated Smagorinsky-Lilly Large Eddy Simulation (LES) based on a Reynolds & Nusselt number correlation is employed to capture the turbulent interfacial heat transfer.

KEY WORDS: VoF; Compressible Vapour; Violent Slosh case; Real gas; Phase Change; Turbulence.

INTRODUCTION

For aerospace applications, LH₂ as a propellant is stored in sub-cooled conditions typically achieved via vapour injection (Moran et al. 1994). During flight, external excitation leads to a drop in tank pressure resulting in the so-called pressure ‘collapse’ effect leading to undesirable saturation conditions. Moreover, heat leaks from the environment produce passive pressurisation (Hasan et al. 1991, Johnson et al. 2024) which lead

to tank pressure build up. Modelling these processes require the accurate correlation between pressure, density, and temperature, but also the accurate prediction of liquid-vapour interfacial mass, heat transfer effects, as well fluid-wall thermal fluxes. This constitutes a truly multi-physics problem where prediction of pressure behaviour inside the tank via a reliable simulation tool is key for design purposes.

To this end, in this work, we employ our simulation cryogenic containment tool, ELEMENTAL® AlphaFlow, on two canonical cases viz. the SHIIVER (Johnson et al. 2024) and Moran experiments (Moran et al. 1994). In the former, we verify the ability of the model to capture passive pressurisation for low wall Biot number calculations. This is to demonstrate accurate modelling of liquid-vapour heat and mass transfer effects as well as accurate prediction of wall-fluid heat fluxes. In the second case, we consider the non-linear violent lateral slosh of a previously pressurised tank.

NUMERICAL THEORY

Governing Equations

Fluid Modelling

The fluid model employed in this work is ELEMENTAL®’s newly developed AlphaFlow Volume-of-Fluid (VoF) weakly-compressible non-isothermal model. Here the liquid is modelled as incompressible and the gas as fully compressible. The two employed Equation-of-State (EoS) are ideal and real gas models. Further, the mass transfer source term is applied to the bulk phases away from the interface as per Hardt & Wondra (2008).

Passive Pressurisation Biot Number Analysis

The passive pressurisation case considered in this work is the SHIIVER experiment (Johnson et al. 2021) where a high heat static flux passive pressurisation case is considered. Here we motivate the use of the Conjugate-Heat-Transfer (CHT) thin wall model via a Biot number analysis where experimental data is pre-emptively used.

From the work by White (2016), a maximum of no more than 5% in error is made in estimating the wall temperature via a thin wall model provided that the Biot number for both phases satisfies the following condition:

$$Bi_p = \frac{h_{c_p} l_w}{k_w} \leq 0.1, \quad (1)$$

with subscript w denoting the solid wall, l_w the characteristic wall thickness ($l_w = 11$ mm) and k_w wall thermal conductivity. Wall properties are computed using the average pressure and temperature recorded by Johnson et al. (2021). Further h_{c_p} is the heat transfer coefficient which in turn is related to the fluid Nusselt number:

$$Nu_p = \frac{h_{c_p} l_p}{k_p}. \quad (2)$$

Bejan (2013) provides empirical correlations for uniform heat flux for a flat vertical wall of length l_p :

$$Ra_p = \frac{g \beta_p l_p^4 \dot{q}}{a_p \nu_p k_p}, \quad (3)$$

where g is acceleration due to gravity, β_p phase expansion coefficient, a_p phase thermal diffusivity, \dot{q} is the maximum heat flux as per Table 2 and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

The Rayleigh number is related to the Nusselt number as:

$$Nu \sim \begin{cases} Ra_p^{\frac{1}{2}} & \text{if } Pr_p \geq 1 \\ (Ra_p Pr_p)^{\frac{1}{5}} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

with Pr_p the Prandtl number expressed as:

$$Pr_p = \frac{c_{p_p} \mu_p}{k_p}. \quad (5)$$

Table 1 Phase Rayleigh, Nusselt heat transfer and Biot number calculation.

t (s)	\bar{p} (Pa)	\bar{T} (K)	Phase	Ra	Nu	h_c	Bi
0	1.42×10^5	23.6	Gas	4.14×10^{16}	1728	17.7	0.0686
0	1.42×10^5	21.6	Liquid	7.09×10^{14}	864	44.8	0.207
1653.65	2.62×10^5	45.4	Gas	2.45×10^{15}	991	18.0	0.0347
1653.65	2.62×10^5	22.1	Liquid	5.24×10^{14}	808	42.0	0.189

Table 2 Measured heat fluxes in each tank region during Baseline test (Johnson et al. 2024).

Forward dome		Barrel		Aft dome	
Sensor ID	Heat flux, [W · m ⁻²]	Sensor ID	Heat flux, [W · m ⁻²]	Sensor ID	Heat flux, [W · m ⁻²]
HFS01	143	HFS09	196	HFS05	155
HFS02	105	HFS10	210	HFS06	129
HFS03	125	HFS11	194	HFS07	138
HFS04	94	HFS12	160	HFS08	117

Method	Forward dome	Barrel	Aft dome	Unit
Conduction	157.84	190.68	134.09	W · m ⁻²
Radiation	114.29	127.00	63.53	W · m ⁻²
Measured	108.24	126.83	54.48	W · m ⁻²
Average	126.79	148.17	84.03	W · m ⁻²

Note that (4) is adapted for the SHIVER tank which is spherical in geometry with a cylindrical portion. For the vapour phase (conservative), the internal radius ($R = 1$ m) is used while the submerge barrel height is used for the liquid phase. As per Table 1 bottom, the vapour Biot number is at least an order below 0.1 while liquid Biot number is approximately 0.2 (above 0.1). Since wall heat flux into the vapour region dominates the rate of pressurisation and the variation in liquid temperatures are small, the thin wall model is employed.

Spatial Discretisation

In ELEMENTAL®, a vertex-centred edge-based Finite Volume median dual-cell approach is used for unstructured spatial discretisation. This differs to the majority of multi-phase codes which employ the cell-centred variant instead. The vertex-centred method is preferred in this work for its provably stable properties on arbitrary meshes (Nordström et al. 2003). Sharp and volume conservative advection of the liquid-gas interface is achieved via the algebraic Higher Resolution Artificial Compressive (HiRAC) scheme (Malan et al. 2021). The thin wall CHT model is solved via an implicit-explicit (imex) temporal integration method (Ascher et al. 1997).

Heat Transfer Discretisation

The thermal conductive term at the liquid vapor interface is discretised using two approaches which depends on whether phase change is switched on/off. In the absence of phase change, a classic “diffused” (Tryggvason et al. 2011, Saade et al. 2023) discretisation approach is employed where the thermal conductivity at the face is weighted with respect to the volume fraction field.

In the presence of phase change, a sharp discretisation of the conductive term is employed. For this purpose, the interface is reconstructed via the PieceWise Linear Interface Conservative (PLIC) (Ilangakoon & Malan 2022) method. This provides a volume conservative reconstruction of the interface and interfacial area for phase change.

Sharp Mass Transfer Model

In the case where the flow is fully resolved, phase change is included where the mass transfer source term $\dot{\rho}_0$ is computed directly (sharply) from phase temperature gradients

$$\dot{\rho}_0^{t+1} = \frac{[k_l \nabla T_l - k_g \nabla T_g] \cdot \hat{n}_\Gamma |^{t+1}}{h_{fg} \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{A}_\Gamma^{t+1}, \quad (6)$$

where h_{fg} denotes the latent heat of vaporisation, \hat{n}_Γ the interfacial normal defined to point out of the vapour phase, and \mathcal{A}_Γ is the interfacial area.

LES model

To qualitatively model pressure drop effects at large Reynolds numbers during sloshing, a calibrated Large Eddy Simulation (LES) turbulence model based on Smagorinsky-Lilly (SGS) (Smagorinsky 1963, Lilly 1966) is employed. This calibration was done using a wide range of experimental data (including proprietary) and produces mesh independent results. Note that this data set did not include the violent test case being modelled in this article.

NUMERICAL VALIDATION

SHIVER Passive Pressurisation Experiment

A series of passive pressurisation experiments were recently conducted for various heat fluxes and fill levels of LH₂. Experiments were conducted in the Structural Heat Intercept Insulation Vibration and Evaluation Rig (SHIVER) (Johnson et al. 2024) shown in Figure 1 (first row). The tank is made from stainless steel 304L with an internal diameter 2 m, and height of 3.3 m (Figure 1 second row).

The tank structure is subdivided into three regions: the forward dome (top ellipsoid), the barrel (mid-section cylinder) and the aft dome (lower ellipsoid), with flanges in both the forward and aft domes. The tank has a total internal volume of 31.1 m³. The wall thickness is 11.0 mm. Insulation is achieved via an MLI blanket where in addition, a Spray On Foam Insulation (SOFI) is applied directly to the tank outer wall and lies below the MLI.

Grid Label	No. of Elements	Interfacial Normal Spacing [mm]	Wall Normal Spacing [mm]
3 mm	5686	6	3
2 mm	7207	4	2
1 mm	23 095	2	1

Property	Notation	Value	Unit
Gas Density	ρ_g	1.99	$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
Specific Gas Constant	R_g	3950.8	$\text{J}\cdot(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
Specific Heat Isobaric Gas	c_{p_g}	10 522.3	$\text{J}\cdot(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
Gas Viscosity	μ_g	Power Law: $8.64 \times 10^{-8} (T_g)^{0.845}$	$\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Gas Thermal Conductivity	k_g	Power Law: $0.00143 (T_g)^{0.839}$	$\text{W}\cdot(\text{mK})^{-1}$
Liquid Density	ρ_l	68.40	$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
Specific Heat Isochoric/Isoobaric Liquid	c_{p_l}	11 035.3	$\text{J}\cdot(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})^{-1}$
Liquid Viscosity	μ_l	1.15×10^{-5}	$\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Liquid Thermal Conductivity	k_l	0.1036	$\text{W}\cdot(\text{mK})^{-1}$
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	β_l	0.020	K^{-1}
Surface Tension Coefficient	σ	0.0017502	$\text{N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$
Initial Pressure	p_0	175.724	kPa
Reference Temperature	T_0	22.38	K

Fig. 3 SHIVER – First row: OH Grid Topology with delineation of different boundary zones. Second row: Mesh metrics. Third row: Ideal gas material properties.

Fig. 4 SHIVER – Documented heat fluxes for forward dome, barrel and aft dome (Johnson et al. 2024).

The experiment chosen for this work is a 70% fill-level passive pressurisation case categorised as per Johnson et al. (2024) under the Baseline Test series. The wall surface is mounted with various pressure, temperature, fill level and heat flux sensors. In each region of the tank, a set of four heat flux sensors are used where their positions are shown in Figure 1 (third row labelled HFS) with the heat fluxes measured by each sensor recorded in Table 2 (first row). Due to the large heat supplied, nucleate boiling is dominant over the initial transients of pressurisation and slows down after. Since nucleate boiling is not modelled in this work, the initial transients are skipped. Instead, the start of the simulation is 226.33 s as per Figure 2 (first row) denoted t_i and corresponds to the time at which the saturation curve intersects sensor SD75's temperature curve. This is chosen as nucleate boiling has ceased while the liquid level is clear from the intersection between the saturation line (dotted red line) and measured temperatures.

In addition to ensuring that the correct convection currents are set up and that the wall is hot at the target start time t_i , the simulation is started 200 s prior. This allows for the initial transients to steady out once the target start time is reached corresponding to an actual start time of 26.33 s (t_0). The pressurisation target of 274.4 kPa from 139.7 kPa is reached just below half an hour corresponding to a total simulated time of 1653.65 s (t_f). The measured pressure increase for this 70% fill level is given in Figure 2 (second row) and is used for comparison. The tank domain used for the numerical case was simplified to exclude the upper and lower lids with the flanges omitted as shown in Figure 3

Fig. 5 SHIVER – Left: Initial temperature at $t = 26.33$ s (left). Right: Temperature profile at $t = 1653.65$ s with superimposed velocity streamlines (right).

Fig. 7 SHIVER – Mass conservation.

Case	dp/dt Pa·s ⁻¹	$\varepsilon(dp/dt)$ [%]
3 mm (RG)	69.2371	2.3469
2 mm (RG)	69.0484	2.0679
1 mm (RG)	67.6539	0.0066
2 mm (IG)	55.8876	17.3865
Experiment	67.6495	-

Fig. 6 SHIVER – First row: Pressurisation rate for ideal and real gas. Second row: Pressure gradient computed between t_i to t_f and corresponding error with respect to experiment value.

(first row) but care was taken to ensure that the total tank volume and internal height matched the experimental test case. The recorded pressure and temperature at t_0 was used as initial conditions (Figure 2 third row). Due to discrepancies in the measured heat flux sensors, Johnson et al. (2024) also provided both a radiative and conductive model to infer

the total heat applied to each region based on wall temperature in addition to the measured heat flux. This is summarised in Figure 4 (second row). The heat flux boundary conditions applied to each region in this work is an average of these fluxes indicated by a red dot in Figure 4 and summarised in Table 2 (second row). The employed grid is an OH topology with interface, wall spacing and cell count as per the second table in Figure 3. The gas is modelled as both ideal and real but the liquid is a strictly Boussinesq incompressible fluid. Surface tension is included with a 90° contact angle at the wall due an assumed dry-out of the meniscus. The ideal gas and constant liquid properties are given in Figure 3 (third row) while the real gas properties are linearly interpolated from CoolProp (Bell et al. 2014) for orthohydrogen. The thin wall properties employed were obtained from the NIST database (Johnson 2024). The Smagorinsky-Lilly LES model is used as turbulence model with a maximum upper viscosity ratio of 2.

In Figure 5, the colour map of the temperature at the start and end of pressurisation is shown. A stratified temperature profile results with compressed liquid leading to a sub-cooled tank. The pressurisation rate for the tested meshes are also shown in Figure 6 (second row). Initially, the pressurisation diverges due to the presence of initial transients due to the lack of initial wall temperature data. However, after t_i , the pressurisation rate with the real gas model computed between t_i and t_f converges to within 2% on coarser meshes and 0.01% on the finest mesh with respect to the experimental value (see Figure 6). The ideal gas model however divergences by up to 20% from the experimental pressurisation rate and hence no finer grids were tested. In Figure 7, machine mass conservation is observed. This validates the developed real gas EoS and confirms the ability of the model to accurately capture passive pressurisation.

Moran Slosh Experiment

Extensive slosh experiments with liquid and slush hydrogen were conducted in the early nineties at the NASA Glen research centre (Hasan

et al. 1991, Moran et al. 1994). Of interest is the experiment by Moran et al. (1994) involving a spherical tank of volume 1.76 m^3 . The latter is: (i) actively pressurised (ramp up stage), (ii) allowed to settle under normal gravity (hold stage), and finally subjected to a lateral excitation (slosh stage). This is illustrated in Figure 10 (second row). The tank was made up of Aluminium (see Figure 10 first row) where slosh was achieved via a shaker.

In this work, we focus on the lateral slosh stage where the chosen regime is in the unstable non-linear (violent) mode. Specifically, a 36% ullage volume fill level with an applied lateral excitation of frequency (f) 0.74 Hz and amplitude (A) of 38.1 mm is modelled. This regime is chosen to demonstrate the ability of the code to capture the so-called pressure drop effects at high Reynolds numbers. Consistent with the experimental setup, a ramp up of 10 s is used. The applied acceleration is expressed as $\mathbf{a} = -(2\pi f)^2 \sin(2\pi f t) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_x$, with the ramp up as per Figure 10 (third row).

Grid Label	No. of Elements	Average Edge Length [mm]
12	131 000	41.6

Fig. 8 Moran Slosh Experiment - 3D OH grid topology.

Fig. 9 Moran Slosh Experiment – Fluid temperatures used for initialisation taken from Gambioli et al. (2025).

Fig. 10 Moran Slosh Experiment – First row: Tank schematic (Moran et al. 1994). Second row: Ramp, hold and slosh stage with simulation start time indicated with a red vertical line. Third row: Acceleration profile with ramp up.

Note for this case we do not model any CHT or phase change effects. The contributions of phase change to the pressure drop rate as compared to the effect of the applied excitation is assumed small. Moreover, the tank is initialised directly using the pre-slosh temperature profile given by Gambioli et al. (2025) as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 11 Moran Slosh Experiment - First row: Interface modes of slosh: (i) lateral slosh followed by ‘swirl’ slosh mode. Second row: Pressure comparison with experiment.

Here, vapour closure is achieved via an ideal gas model. An OH grid topology as shown in Figure 8 is used to model this case with mesh metrics as per Table 8. In Figure 11 (first and second row), two modes of slosh are seen: (i) a lateral slosh mode (top and bottom left) and a self excited swirl mode (bottom right). In Figure 11 (third row), we plot the computed pressure drop rate v. the experimental result. An excellent match is seen demonstrating the ability of the solver to capture pressure

drop effects at high Reynolds numbers.

CONCLUSION

In this work, ELEMENTAL®’s weakly-compressible AlphaFlow simulation tool is applied and assessed on two canonical test cases for LH₂ containment modelling, viz. the passive pressurisation and slosh. The model also employs a thin wall CHT model where the thin wall assumption is confirmed via a Biot number analysis. Sharp or diffused interface liquid-vapour heat transfer model is employed depending on whether phase change is included or not. The mass transfer source term is computed via a gradient based method with the gradients computed via a least squares method.

For the tested SHIIVER experiment, both an ideal and real gas are modelled as well CHT and phase change effects. The employed grid is an OH topology initialised using the experimental temperature profile. Stratified temperature profiles are shown with interface being stable throughout the simulation. The pressurisation rates agree within 2% on the coarsest grid and 0.01% on the finest grid.

Finally, the model is evaluated on its ability to capture the so-called pressure collapse effects. Here, the ideal gas model is employed while CHT and phase change effects are not modelled. An unstable regime of slosh is selected for the purpose of validating the model at high Reynolds numbers. An OH grid topology is again employed where the initial temperature profile is obtained from Gambioli et al. (2025). Two slosh modes are observed: (i) a lateral slosh and (ii) a swirl mode. The accompanied numerical pressure drop rate shows an excellent agreement with experimental trends.

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